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COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF TESTING THE ACETYLRARY STATUS OF PATIENTS WITH CHEMICAL EYE BURNS

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted on 150 patients with chemical burns of the eyes who were hospitalized in the republican clinical ophthalmological hospital of the ministry of health of the republic of Uzbekistan. The calculation of economic efficiency was carried out according to Yunkerov V.I., Grigoryev S.G. (2002) in the modification of Mirsaidov E.M. and using methods for assessing the economic effectiveness of the compared options. According to the results of the study, it was found that an individualized approach to the management of patients with chemical burns of the eyes gives greater economic efficiency than a standardized approach to the management of such patients, considering the costs of determining their acetylar status, and the average cost per patient was 299,720 UZS; the method of individualization of patients with determination of their acetylation phenotype is economically less expensive and easy to perform compared to the method of determining human leukocyte antigens (HLA) histocompatibility and the savings when comparing the cost of carrying out these test methods was 413000 UZS per single study in favor of the method of determining acetylation phenotype.

Keywords: cost effectiveness, standardized and individualized approaches, chemical burns of eyes, phenotype of acetylation.

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ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ТЕСТИРОВАНИЯ АЦЕТИЛЯРНОГО СТАТУСА У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ХИМИЧЕСКИМИ ОЖОГАМИ ГЛАЗ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Обследование проводилось в Республиканской клинической офтальмологической больнице у 150 пациентов, находившихся на стационарном лечении с ожогом органа зрения. Расчет экономической эффективности проводили по Юнкерову В.И., Григорьеву С.Г. в модификации Мирсаидова Э.М. и с использованием методов оценки экономической эффективности сравниваемых вариантов (2002). По результатам проверок определено что, индивидуализированный подход к ведению пациентов с химическими ожогами глаз дает большую экономическую эффективность, чем стандартизованный подход к ведению таких больных, с учетом затрат на определение их ацетилярного статуса, а экономия на 1 пациента в среднем составляет от 299720 сўм. Метод индивидуализации пациентов с определением их фенотипа ацетилирования экономически менее затратен и легко выполним по сравнению с методом определения HLA гистосовместимости и экономия при сравнении затратности на проведение указанных методов тестирования составляет 413000 сўм на одно исследование в пользу метода определения ФА.

Ключевые слова: экономическая эффективность, стандартный и индивидуальный подход, химический ожог глаз, фенотип ацетилирования.

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КЎЗНИНГ КИМЁВИЙ КУЙИШИ БЎЛГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА АЦЕТИЛЯР СТАТУСИ ҲОЛАТИНИ ҚЎЛЛАШДА ИҚТИСОДИЙ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Текширув ЎзР ССВ Республика клиник офтальмология шифохонасида, кўрув аъзосининг куйиш касаллиги билан стационар даволанишда бўлган 150 нафар беморларда ўтказилган. Иқтисодий самарадорликни ҳисоблаб чиқиш Мирсаидов Э.М. модификацияси ва қиёсий вариантларни иқтисодий самарадорлигини баҳолаш усулларида фойдаланган ҳолда Юнкер В.И., Григорьев С.Г. (2002) бўйича ўтказилди. Текширувлар натижаси бўйича шу нарса аниқландики, кўрув аъзосининг куйиш касаллиги бўлган беморларни даволашни олиб боришда индивидуал ёндашувларни қўллаш шундай беморларни олиб боришда стандартлашган ёндашувга қараганда катта иқтисодий самарадорликни беради, уларни ацетиляр статусини аниқлашга кетган сарф - харажатларни ҳисобга олган ҳолда, иқтисод эса 1 нафар бемор учун ўртача 299720 минг сўмни ташкил қилади. Беморларни ацетирлаш фенотипини аниқлаш билан бирга уларни индивидуализациялаш услуги гистомосликни HLA ни аниқлаш услубига қараганда иқтисодий томондан камроқ сарфланади ва осон бажарилади ва кўрсатиб ўтилган услубларни тестлаштирилиши ўтказилганда кетган сарф - харажатлар билан солиштирганда иқтисодиёт ацетирланиш фенотипини аниқлаш фойдасига битта текширув учун 413000 минг сўмни ташкил қилади.

Калит сўзлар: иқтисодий самарадорлик, стандартлашган ва индивидуал ёндашув, кўзларни кимёвий куйиши, ацетирлаш фенотипи.

Relevance. It is possible to obtain the maximum result at minimum cost only if a comprehensive medical and economic analysis of medical care (MC) is carried out in a timely manner with a simultaneous consideration of medical, social and economic effects in the context of preserving and increasing human capital [7].

As you know, the calculation of costs per patient with a chemical eye burn consists of the costs on the part of the patient himself and the costs on the part of the state. The costs on the part of the patient in the absence of health insurance, in general, are reduced to transportation costs, payment for certain laboratory and instrumental research methods and drugs that are not included in the list of free services in the provision of medical care to patients from primary health care to specialized care in public centers or private medical institutions and clinics [2,8]. The second category of expenditures is public expenditures, which consist of the following expenditure items: payment for days of incapacity for work of the patient, if he works in the public service for those periods of incapacity for work due to this disease, while on outpatient, inpatient treatment, for the period of rehabilitation due to temporary disability, and if the patient becomes disabled, then the payment of a grant (pension) for disability, taking into account temporary or permanent disability, including when providing any benefits provided by state legislation [6,9]. The next category of public expenditures is for the remuneration of medical workers (remuneration of a GP doctor, ophthalmologists at the stages of therapy, ophthalmologists-surgeons, if a surgical intervention is performed, an anesthesiologist, if anesthesia is performed, etc., laboratory assistants during necessary laboratory tests, nurses, nurses, etc.) [3,4]. The next expense item is the cost of standard and special procedures and studies to clarify the diagnosis, dynamic examination and monitoring of the patient, and the cost of drugs provided by the national protocol for the treatment of this patient at the stages of therapy. If the patient needs inpatient treatment, then the items of expenses associated with his hospitalization, stay in the hospital, according to the consumables provided for patients of the corresponding profile, are added. In this case, it may be necessary to invite related specialists and conduct additional types of examination and therapy [5].

In this regard, the aim of the study was to reduce material costs both at the state and private levels by applying methods that allow individualizing approaches to therapy, predicting the development and course of the process, the formation of complications and outcomes of eye burn injury in patients.

The need for an individual approach to patient management was clearly demonstrated by the COVID-19 pandemic, when in different regions of the world, the same patients with COVID-19 could not be managed according to the schemes offered by doctors from various clinics in Europe, the USA, and Southeast Asian countries, CIS, etc. Moreover, in the same regions, doctors came to the conclusion about the need for an individualized approach to each case of the disease, and patient management according to the recommendations of even such serious organizations as WHO, the US Institute of Health, CDC, the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation, etc. sometimes led to aggravation of patients, an increase in the frequency of complications with a high level of mortality. And as a result, all highly qualified specialists were inclined to the need for an individualized approach to managing patients in each case, which not only made it possible to better assess the condition of patients, prescribe therapy based on the characteristics of the patient's body, but also achieve more favorable outcomes of the disease [1,11, 12.15].

The purpose of the study. Based on the foregoing and taking into account current trends in an individualized approach to managing patients, but taking into account National and international protocols, at the first stage of calculating the cost-effectiveness, we considered it appropriate to compare individualization methods for the approach to therapy using the method for determining HLA typing and the method for determining the phenotype of acetylation (FA).

Material and methods of research. The calculation of economic efficiency was carried out according to Junkerov V.I., Grigoriev S.G. in the modification of Mirsaidov E.M. [10] and using methods for assessing the economic efficiency of the compared options [13].

As a result of a comprehensive analysis of 350 patients (aged 18 to 65 years) admitted for treatment at the Republican Clinical Ophthalmological Hospital of the Ministry of Health of the

Republic of Uzbekistan, 150 patients were identified with damage to the organ of vision after a chemical burn, in 103 of which FA was determined. We compared the cost estimates for general studies and for studies with individualization of patients (for determination of HLA status and determination of FA) according to standard methods of Terasaky P.L., Mecllelland J.D. (1964) and Brodie BB, Axelrod J, et al. (1949) modified by Popov T.A. and Leonenko O.B (1977), respectively. The cost minimization analysis is calculated by the following formula:

$CMA = DC1 - DC2$, where

- SMA - an indicator of the difference in costs,
- DC1 — direct costs when applying the 1st method (FA),
- DC2 - direct costs when applying the 2nd method (HLA).

Result. The calculation of economic efficiency was carried out as follows: first, the costs of general clinical testing of patients (150 people) were determined to diagnose damage to the organ of vision and the process of reparation of eye tissues after a chemical burn. Further summed up with the costs of individualizing the status of patients to determine their acetyl status (FA) and HLA testing (the most well-known and proven method):

Calculation of research costs in determining FA and general clinical laboratory examination of patients was:

Stest / Ap (CN + Szp) / 150 * (87,000 + 9000) / 14,400,000 UZS At the same time, the determination of FA is carried out directly by the attending physician, no specialized training is required and can be carried out in a standard biochemical laboratory of the clinic with a study of the urine of patients (non-invasive method) after taking Norsulfazol, an inexpensive method taking into account all costs:

CN= DI*CI+Nr = 87,000 soums (according to the tariff) per patient Stest is the cost of spending on a general clinical analysis in 150 patients to diagnose the nature of reparative processes and the development of complications in chemical burns;

Ap - The average number of tested patients (150), to identify patients after a chemical burn with a different phenotype of acetylation (FA);

DI - Quantity by type of consumables (chemical reagents) used for analysis for FA of one patient (I = 1,2,.....,N);

CI - Cost by type of consumables (chemical reagents) used for one patient;

CN - Average cost of consumables (chemicals);

Nr - overhead costs.

Szp - The cost of remuneration of medical personnel for conducting a clinical analysis per patient:

$Szp = Szpvr + Zzpcm / 6000 + 3000 / 9000$ UZS

Szpvr - salary of a biochemist per unit of time;

Szpsm - wages of paramedical personnel.

Next, we determined the costs of conducting clinical (Sskd) diagnosis of patients (150 persons) after a chemical burn with testing of HLA status with blood sampling from the patient (invasive method) and a complex method for determining the individual characteristics of the patient, which requires a specially trained laboratory assistant immunologist, special equipment and consumables, which on average cost from 500,000 UZS (it should also be noted that the various methods of patient individualization offered today are also invasive, expensive, requiring special equipment and conditions for analysis: IL 28b; MPB2, etc.)

Next, in a similar way, we calculate the cost of the study for 150 patients to calculate the cost of a complex study of the individual properties of the patient's body based on HLA testing:

$Tm = DJ * CJ + MN = (D1 * C1 + D2 * C2 + D3 * C3) + MN = 500\ 000$ UZS

$Sskd = Ab * (Tm + Zzp) / 150 * (500,000 + 9000) / 76,350,000$ UZS

Where:

DJ - Quantity by type of consumables (chemical reagents) used for clinical diagnosis of one patient (J = 1,2,.....,N);

CJ - Cost by type of consumables (chemical reagents) used for clinical diagnosis of one patient;

T_m - The cost of complex clinical diagnosis by HLA testing per patient.

Thus, the economic effect (E) due to the application of the proposed method is determined by:

$E_{150} = S_{skd} - S_{pen} = 76,350,000 - 14,400,000 = 61,950,000$ soums

Only according to the results of this study on the individualization of the status of the patient, the savings per 1 patient is $E_{150} = 61,950,000 : 150 = 413,000$ UZS

Where n is the number of studies (150 people) So, according to the results of the analysis using testing for FA, it can be stated that if, with the previously given two options for diagnosing a limited contingent of patients, the economic effect per 1 patient when using the method for determining FA is 413,000 UZS, for 150 persons - respectively 61.95 million soums, then throughout the country this indicator can increase tenfold, taking into account the frequency of this pathology in ophthalmic practice.

The next step in calculating the economic efficiency was an individualized approach to the management and therapy of patients with chemical eye burns who were hospitalized at the Republican Clinical Ophthalmological Hospital of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the acetylation phenotype and without determining this indicator.

When determining FA in patients, it is possible to individualize approaches to the management and therapy of patients depending on the rate of xenobiotic acetylation (remains of a damaging agent, necrotic tissues and the implementation of an inflammatory process) and the processes of repair of eye tissues after a chemical eye burn. At the same time, it should be taken into account that standardized management of patients with eye burns is most effective only at the stages of initial early treatment of patients. Further, taking into account FA, we have shown that the process of burn injury proceeds differently in patients with different FA. So, for slow acetylators (MA) protracted sluggish processes are more characteristic, with a long, recurrent course with a slow effect, including, for example, when prescribing antibiotic therapy. With such a protracted course, as a rule, we are forced to prescribe antibiotic therapy (AB therapy) for a long time, not taking into account that this does not contribute to a more effective implementation of the inflammatory process, because the process itself tends to be delayed due to the slow elimination of patients from the body decay products and necrotic tissues after a burn. In this case, long-term prescription of antibiotics will not only not accelerate convalescence, but can also aggravate the condition of patients due to the systemic effect of antibacterial drugs on general immunity, thereby creating the possibility for viral, fungal and other types of infections. In addition, in view of the ability of almost 70% of all drugs to be utilized through the liver (enterohepatic and / or hematohepatoenteric circulation), this can lead to the development of a hepatotoxic effect, which can also exacerbate the inflammatory process and cause an increase in treatment costs. patients. In this case, patients with MA need to shorten the time for prescribing AB therapy and, along with AB therapy, they must add general and local immunomodulatory agents to the treatment; means of correcting intestinal biocenosis and hepatoprotective therapy to reduce possible complications and improve the prognosis of outcomes of burn eye injury.

Speaking about fast acetylators (BAs), we must keep in mind that everything happens much faster with them than with the average statistical accounting and the average approach, without individualization in the management and treatment of patients with chemical eye burns. Thus, using the same antibiotic therapy as an example, which is included in the national standards for the management of patients with chemical burn injuries of the eyes, it should be taken into account in patients with BA that antibiotics are eliminated much faster in them than with an average prescription. On the one hand, this can reduce the expected effect of this type of therapy - an undertreated process, and also necessitate a higher dose of the drug and its longer prescription, on the other hand. Taking into account the above, an individualized approach to the management of patients with chemical eye burns based on the determination of their FA will not only contribute to more effective treatment of these patients, but also save a sufficient amount of funds and resources in the management of these patients.

In connection with the above, we calculated cost-effectiveness in the treatment of patients based on the analysis of average costs per patient, taking into account an individualized approach or a standardized approach to the treatment of patients with chemical eye burns.

The calculation of economic efficiency was carried out similarly to the above method, but as a calculation unit we used the average cost per patient per day based on therapy regulated in the National Protocol of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the management of patients with chemical eye burns:

$CI = DI + CI + Nf = 130.000 \text{ UZS} + 20.500 \text{ UZS} + 42.860 \text{ UZS} = 193360 \text{ UZS}$ (according to the tariff of the Republican Clinical Ophthalmological Hospital of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan) per patient;

Where:

CI - average total costs per patient per day;

DI - the cost of one bed/day of the patient's stay in the hospital;

CI - cost of food for 1 day;

Nf is the average cost of drug therapy per patient per day.

CN is the cost of treatment of all patients with chemical eye burns;

Ap - The average number of examined patients (150), to determine the total cost of treatment with the use of drug therapy;

Stest - the cost of the study for an individualized approach, using the method for determining FA per patient;

Tdn - the total duration of the patient's stay in the hospital for treatment in days;

Z1 is the average cost of treatment of 1 patient with a chemical eye burn without individualization of therapy (standardized approach);

$$Z1 = CI \times Tdn1$$

In the course of the analysis of 47 patients who were treated in a standardized way without testing them for FA, the average length of stay in the hospital for 1 patient was 7.2 ± 0.49 days ($Td1 = 7$ days).

Therefore, the average cost of inpatient treatment of 1 patient according to a standardized method is: $Z1 = CI \times Tday1 = 193360 \text{ UZS} \times 7 \text{ days} = 1353520 \text{ UZS}$.

Further, in a similar way, we calculated the costs per 1 patient with an individualized approach to therapy with the determination of FA.

Z2 - the average cost of treatment of 1 patient with a chemical eye burn with individualization of therapy by testing for FA:

$$Z2 = CI \times Tdn2 + Stest;$$

In this calculation option, the cost of the FA study (Stest) is added - according to the tariff = 87000 soums

An analysis of 103 patients who were treated in an individualized way with testing for FA showed that the average length of stay in the hospital for 1 patient was 4.9 ± 0.26 days ($Tdn2 = 5$ days). Based on this, the average cost of inpatient treatment of 1 patient according to an individualized method with the determination of additional FA is: $Z2 = CI \times Tdn2 + Stest = 193360 \text{ UZS} \times 5 \text{ days} + 87000 \text{ UZS} = 1053800 \text{ UZS}$.

To calculate the cost-effectiveness per 1 patient of the compared approaches to therapy, we looked at the difference in the costs of inpatient treatment in these two groups:

$$E1 = Z1 - Z2 = 1353520 \text{ UZS} - 1053800 \text{ UZS} = 299720 \text{ UZS}$$

Thus, based on the calculation of cost-effectiveness, it was found that even the addition of testing for FA in patients with chemical eye burn is more cost-effective than a standardized approach to the treatment of these patients. The savings per 1 patient is 299720 UZS, and when calculated for 150 patients with chemical eye burns:

$$E150 = E1 \times n = 299720 \text{ UZS} \times 150 = 44,958,000 \text{ UZS}$$

As we have already indicated, we calculated only the use of only those drugs that were regulated in the list of the Republican Clinical Ophthalmological Hospital of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and if we take into account other pathogenetic drugs used in the treatment of patients with chemical eye burns (anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, resolving, accelerating regeneration fabrics, etc.), then the economic effect will be even more significant, both in terms of public funding and private investment (patient, sponsors, etc.).

Based on the foregoing, it follows that an individualized approach to the management of patients with chemical eye burns is more cost-effective than a standardized approach to the management of such patients.

In this regard, we analyzed the cost of various methods of individualizing patient management and, for comparison, took our proposed method for determining FA and testing the HLA status of patients [14].

Next, we determined the costs of conducting clinical (Sskd) diagnosis of patients (150 persons) after a chemical burn with testing of HLA status with blood sampling from the patient (invasive method) and a complex method for determining the individual characteristics of the patient, which requires a specially trained laboratory assistant immunologist, special equipment and consumables, which on average cost from 500,000 soums (it should also be noted that the various methods of patient individualization offered today are also invasive, even more expensive, requiring special equipment and conditions for analysis: IL 28b; MPB2 and etc.)

Further, in a similar way, we calculated the cost of the study for 150 patients to calculate the cost of a complex study of the individual properties of the patient's body based on HLA testing:

$$T_m = DJ * CJ + MN = (D_1 * C_1 + D_2 * C_2 + D_3 * C_3) + MN = 500\,000 \text{ UZS.}$$

$$\text{Sskd} \text{ Ab} * (T_m + Z_{zp}) \text{ } 150 * (500,000 + 9000) \text{ } 76,350,000 \text{ UZS.}$$

Where:

DJ - Quantity by type of consumables (chemical reagents) used for clinical diagnosis of one patient (J = 1,2,...,N);

CJ - Cost by type of consumables (chemical reagents) used for clinical diagnosis of one patient;

T_m - Cost of complex clinical diagnosis by HLA testing per patient

Thus, the economic effect (E) due to the application of the proposed method is determined by:
E_{150 / Sskd - Spen} = 76,350,000 - 14,400,000 = 61,950,000 UZS.

Only according to the results of this study on the individualization of the status of the patient, the savings per 1 patient is

$$E_1 / E_{150} = 61,950,000 : 150 = 413,000 \text{ UZS;}$$

Where n is the number of studies (150 people)

Conclusions:

1. An individualized approach to the management of patients with chemical eye burns provides greater economic efficiency than a standardized approach to the management of such patients, taking into account the costs of determining their acetylar status, and the savings per 1 patient average from 299,720 UZS;

2. The method of individualization of patients with the determination of their FA is economically less expensive and easy to perform compared to the method for determining HLA histocompatibility and savings when comparing the cost of conducting these testing methods is 413,000 UZS study in favor of the method for determining FA.

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